

vigor scale of 1 and high ratoon rating. Crosses involving IET6709 and IET7552 as one of the parents had high ratooning ability and ratoon yield. Among the hybrids, IET6709/IET7552 and its

reciprocal registered maximum tillers, with a ratoon vigor scale of 1 and with good ratoon rating; that resulted in high ratoon yield. ■

Influence of variety, irrigation, and N level on production of effective ratoon tillers

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We studied the production of effective ratoon tillers in a field trial 1984-85 and 1985-86. Rice varieties Bhavani, Ponni, and IR20 were grown under normal management for the main crop. The

ratoon crops were grown with two irrigation schedules (5 cm water throughout the crop period and 5 cm water 1 d after the disappearance of ponded water) and four N levels (50, 75, 100, and 125 kg N/ha) in a split-plot design with three replications. Main crop plots were harvested separately, at 20-cm high, with one border row left on all sides.

Number of productive ratoon tillers had a direct bearing on productivity. More productive tillers/hill were recovered in the second year than in the first year (Table 1). ■

Table 1. Effect of variety, irrigation, and N level (50, 75, 100, 125 kg N/ha) on productive ratoon tillers/hill.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./hill)									
	1984-85					1985-86				
	50	75	100	125	Mean	50	75	100	125	Mean
Bhavani	9.4	10.4	11.3	11.7	10.7	10.1	11.8	13.1	14.8	12.5
Ponni	6.6	7.6	8.0	8.8	7.7	9.7	11.0	13.0	13.9	11.9
IR20	5.2	5.5	5.6	6.7	5.8	9.9	11.0	12.4	13.4	11.7
Continuous Irrigation (C)	7.3	7.7	7.6	8.3	7.7	10.2	11.5	12.4	13.6	11.9
Intermittent Irrigation (I)	6.8	8.4	9.0	9.8	8.4	9.7	11.0	13.2	14.5	12.1
Bhavani-C	10.1	10.2	10.1	10.6	10.2	10.1	11.3	12.3	13.6	11.8
Bhavani-I	8.8	10.7	12.5	12.7	11.2	10.1	12.4	14.0	16.0	13.1
Ponni-C	6.7	7.5	7.6	8.0	7.5	9.3	11.4	12.7	13.8	11.8
Ponni-I	6.4	7.7	8.3	9.7	8.3	10.1	10.6	13.3	14.1	12.0
IR20-C	5.1	5.3	5.2	6.3	5.5	11.1	12.0	12.3	13.5	12.2
IR20-I	5.4	5.7	6.1	7.0	6.1	8.8	9.9	12.4	13.3	11.1
Mean	7.1	7.9	8.3	9.1		9.9	11.3	12.8	14.0	
Variety (V)				LSD						LSD
Irrigation				2.0						NS
V × C				NS						NS
Nitrogen (N)				NS						NS
V × Irrigation				0.8						0.8
N × V				NS						NS
N × Irrigation				NS						NS

Table 2. Productive tillers and yield of main and ratoon crops.

Variety	1984-85				1985-86			
	Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
Bhavani	10.5	10.7	2.92	1.60	10.5	12.5	5.14	2.94
Ponni	7.2	7.7	2.49	0.96	9.2	11.9	5.33	1.25
IR20	4.5	5.8	3.83	0.32	11.2	11.7	5.57	0.314
LSD	1.5	2.0	0.400	0.073	1.1	ns	ns	0.158

During the first year, Bhavani had the most productive tillers/hill. This may have been due to higher carbohydrate content in the stubble crop and more regeneration capacity. Irrigation level and the interaction of varieties and irrigation level did not influence number of productive tillers. Tiller production under different N levels varied significantly, with an increase in productive tillers with increasing N.

The ratoon crop produced more productive tillers than the main crop both years (Table 2), perhaps because the ratoon crop produced tillers from the top as well as from the basal nodes. Almost all tillers formed in the ratoon crop bear panicles. ■

Growth and yield of rice varieties grown in deep water

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We evaluated growth and yield of 13 promising rice lines developed at different research stations under deep water (up to 80 cm) at Cuttack. The photoperiod-sensitive, long-duration (170-180 d), tall (150-200 cm) cultivars and a local check were sown on 26 May at 400 seeds/m², 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized with 40 kg N, 9 kg P/ha in the furrow. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications.

Water started accumulating in the field at 7 d after emergence (DE) and increased rapidly to 40 cm at 25 DE. It reached maximum depths of 76 and 83 cm at 60 and 100 DE, respectively, then receded gradually to near zero at crop maturity.

Yields in general were low, because panicles/m² were few. Water stress at very early growth stages caused seedling death and adversely affected tillering. Tall cultivars (IET10084, IET10030, IET10029, IET10008, and IET10003) yielded more than 3 t/ha; relatively short cultivars (IET10006, IET9071, IET9017, IET11184, and local check Hathipanja) produced less than 2